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“NEW YEAR’S LOVE”

When the new year has come,
It is the time for new one,
To honour Jesus,
Our Greatest Saviour.

We need to fresh our minds,
Negativities are erased,
The beginning of life,
Praying for holiness.

The new year brings us peace,
It is our happiness,
Remember all memories,
With our families.

I love my mother,
I love my father,
I love my teachers, and
I love my classmates.